

Appendix C: Interview Guide

This is the interview guide for the semi-structured interviews. It is structured in main and follow-up questions, and the numbering of the main questions resembles the order during the interview. Some questions were altered slightly for the independent experts to have an industry-wide perspective instead of a specific company focus. These adaptations are indicated in square brackets. When required, we also asked context-specific spontaneous ad-hoc questions that were not included in the interview guide.

1. Interviewee background:

- (a) Current role and how long in that role?
- (b) Previous roles?
- (c) AI/ML proficiency? — How proficient would you consider yourself when it comes to AI and ML?
- (d) Regulatory requirements background?
- (e) Graduation year?
- (f) Educational background?
- (g) Start year at the current company?

2. How are you adapting your current development practices for AI/ML systems?

- (a) Do you have continuous engineering practices (aka pipelines) in place?
- (b) What is the release frequency or model update frequency of ML models in production?

3. What comes to your mind when you think about the AI Act?

4. From your perspective, to what extent has the upcoming AI Act already been addressed within your organization[/ within the industry]?

- (a) If yes, in what way?
- (b) Which departments have been involved in that so far?

- (c) As of now, what are the priorities at your company when it comes to the AI Act?
5. **High-risk AI Scenario — We now assume that one of your products would classify as a high-risk AI system and therefore needs to comply with the AI Act:**
- (a) *Answered per high-risk requirement:*
 - i. Which methods/approaches/techniques do you already have in place that could be mapped to the requirements?
 - ii. For which requirements are you currently lacking solutions?
 - (b) Which requirements do you consider most challenging to operationalize?
 - (c) Where may external expertise be required?
6. **How big of a challenge do you think is compliance with the AI Act really?**
7. **How do you think the AI Act will impact your company or industry?**
- (a) What are the positive and negative side effects?
8. **Even if you don't plan on developing high-risk AI systems, which parts of the act would you do anyway?**
- (a) What would bring the most value for you, if anything?
9. **Do you have anything more to add?**
10. **Is there anyone else you know who would be a suitable interview partner?**